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ROLE OF HEAVY METAL STRESS IN ALLEVIATING AND PHYTOSTIMULATION OF MICROORGANISMS: DUAL PERFORMANCE WARHORSES IN SOIL BIOREMEDIATION

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Abstract

One of the major challenges faced by agriculture is the reclamation of contaminated soils and the replenishment of soil with necessary nutrients for efficient crop production. Dual-performing microorganisms for alleviating biotic as well as abiotic (heavy metal) stress besides increasing plant yield serve as a promising solution to the current problem. This review is an attempt to understand the use of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) and their ability to withstand heavy metal stress. Both interactions will be discussed in detail i.e., metal-microbe interaction deals with the accumulation, transformation, and detoxification of heavy metals while plant-microbe interaction stimulates growth and improve nutrient uptake in the plant. Bioremediation is preferred over physical and chemical remediation techniques due to its eco-friendly, sustainable, and resource-friendly nature. Different mechanisms used by PGPR like biofertilizers, nitrogen fixation, phosphate solubilization, and production of siderophores and exopolysaccharides, are also explained. Finally, consequences of heavy metal stress in biological systems, mechanisms used in phytoremediation (e.g., phytoextraction, phytovolatilization), effective microorganisms (EM) that increase soil fertility and plant growth mitigating harmful impacts of heavy metals, and internal and external mechanisms of tolerance are explained.

Keywords: heavy metals, phytoremediation, PGPR, soil remediation, stress-tolerance.

Introduction

Agriculture is the main sector of economic growth in developing countries. However, in contemporary production systems, most crops are very demanding regarding the high requirements for fertilizers [1]. On the other hand, every day there is more evidence that the continuous application of nitrogen fertilizers can have negative impacts on agroecosystems, such as nitrate leaching, resource pollution, and gaseous emissions, increase in the content of salts in the soils, causing irreparable damage to the environment and with potential risk to humanity [2]. The foregoing makes it clear that various problems demand permanent attention from researchers. Specifically, a promising method to reduce the use of synthetic fertilizers in agriculture is the application of PGPR (plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria), as microbial inoculants. The use of PGPR as biofertilizers is a sustainable option that favors the availability of nutritional elements and plant growth and yield. Inoculated cultures with PGPR substantially reduce the use of synthetic fertilizers, and negative impacts on the soil, increasing crop yields, thus contributing to the economy of the producer and the feeding of the population [3,4].

One of the distinctive features of modern society is the growing generation of anthropogenic activity and

environmental influences, which brings considerable damage to human health and biological diversity. Heavy metals are pollutants that need special attention because they can stay in the ground for several decades and concentrate on the trophic chains [5-7]. Technologies developed for the sanitation of environments sieved with heavy metals are costly and require a long period before execution. Phytoremediation is a branch of bioremediation that arose recently as an alternative to this environmental problem. It is based on the use of plants that accumulate high concentrations of metals in their tissues to neutralize pollutants [8-18]. Previous studies suggested that rhizospheres' microorganisms can alter the circulation of metals in the environment, with subsequent effects on the plant's potential for root uptake. Currently, phytoremediation is not a commercially available technology. Advances in the field are limited by a lack of knowledge of complex interactions in the rhizosphere and hyperaccumulator plant mechanisms that allow metal translocation and its accumulation [19,20].

Since the end of the 20th century, various technologies have been developed to mitigate the risk of pollution with heavy metals or to clean water and contaminated floors. Many of these are costly and moderately effective, and also require long periods of development

and investigation, in the search for alternatives to new and improved tracks that replace the current sanitation strategies. In this sense, phytoremediation serves as a cheap technology with great potential in soil sanitation and recovery. This technique is based on the use of green plants, including woody species, which contain, remove, or neutralize heavy metals or radionuclides. This definition includes any biological, chemical, or physical process co-induced by plants, which helps in the absorption, sequestration, degradation, and metabolism of pollutants, either by plants themselves or by microorganisms [21].

The possible use of hyperaccumulator plants, especially to detoxify contaminated environments (phytoremediation) currently enhances research with boards of various fields. In this sense, the study of associated microorganisms with metal hyperaccumulator plants and their relationships can provide important insights into foundations [22].

Role of Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) in heavy metal stress tolerance

Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) or plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPM) are the microorganisms that perform dual functions i.e. promoting the growth of plants while degrading or minimizing environmental pollutants from soil [23]. They reside in the rhizosphere of the plants to actively uptake nutrients as well as heavy metals from the soil into plants by transforming them from toxic forms to less toxic or harmless compounds. In the case of PGPR, the most common bacterial genera include *Agrobacterium*, *Azoarcus*, *Bacillus*, *Klebsiella*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Serratia* [24].

According to Mishra et al. [25], bacteria reported for heavy metal tolerance like Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, and Actinobacteria, belong to bacterial species of *Bacillus*, *Arthrobacter*, and *Pseudomonas* as represented in the table 1. Moreover, the important fungal genera reported for heavy metal contamination tolerance include Basidiomycota, Ascomycota, and *Trichoderma*, as mentioned in table 1 below [25,26].

Table 1

The bacterial and fungal species that can withstand the heavy metal stress in soil

Microorganisms	References
<i>Bacillus</i>	[27]
<i>Pseudomonas</i>	[27]
<i>Arthrobacter</i>	[27]
<i>Streptomyces</i>	[28]
<i>Methylobacterium</i>	[28]
<i>Ochrobactrum</i>	[29]
Ascomycota	[30]
Basidiomycota	[30]
<i>Trichoderma</i>	[31,32]
<i>Penicillium</i>	[31,32]
<i>Aspergillus</i>	[31,32]
<i>Mucor</i>	[31,32]

Plant growth-promoting microorganisms include *Bradyrhizobium* sp., such as *B. japonicum* and *B. elkanii* with reported growth of soybean (*Glycine max*) and sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*) [33]. Moreover, some endophytic N₂-fixing bacteria such as *Pantoea*,

Bacillus, and *Klebsiella* promote the growth of plants like *Saccharum officinarum* and *Zea mays* [33]. Among *Herbaspirillum* sp. such as *H. frisingense* promotes the growth of *Oryza sativa*, *Sorghum bicolor*, *Zea mays* and *Hordeum vulgare* [33] as mentioned in table 2.

Table 2

The list of microorganisms reported for promoting the growth of respective crop plants colonizing the plant roots in symbiosis

Microorganisms	Plants	References
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i> sp.	<i>Glycine max</i> , <i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	[34,35]
Endophytic N ₂ -fixing bacteria	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> , <i>Zea mays</i>	[36]
<i>Herbaspirillum</i> sp.	<i>Oryza sativa</i> , <i>Sorghum bicolor</i> , <i>Zea mays</i> , <i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	[37-39]
<i>Azospirillum</i> sp.	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	[40]

Root colonization

Root colonization is the foremost step in the PGPR functioning as without microbial consortia inhabiting the rhizosphere, neither plant growth can be promoted, nor the detoxification of heavy metals can be done. The most important features in microorganisms for successful root colonization are:

- Ability to survive after inoculation

- They should carry out their growth on the primary roots
- Colonization should extend through the entire root system
- Growth of PGPR should also be in the seed region i.e., spermosphere.

Colonization in the spermosphere of the seeds of *Cyperus elegans* (Cyperaceae) and *Echinochloa polystachya* (Poaceae), was an important event to promote the growth of the seedlings obtained. Root colonization by endophytic microorganisms includes four stages: 1) attraction, b) recognition, c) adhesion, and d) invasion which is affected by biotic and abiotic factors. Colonization capacity is a key factor in the prevention and treatment of fungal diseases because the host plants are closely related to biofilm formation; strong colonization leads to adequate biofilm formation. The best crop results depend on adequate colonization of bacteria in the rhizosphere; application via the most adequate inoculation technique so the seeds will be reflected in a higher percentage of germination as well as in the productivity of the crop in addition to increasing its resistance to stress [41]. For example, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, a natural inhabitant of the soil, is predominantly numerous in the rhizosphere microflora of many plant species and are the first to colonize young roots. A lot of these organisms suppress diseases in plants, protecting the roots and seeds from infection by pathogens present in the soil [42].

PGPR mode of action

PGPR has beneficial effects on plants through direct and indirect mechanisms. The direct mechanisms occur when bacteria synthesize metabolites that facilitate plants, or when they increase the availability of different nutritional elements, required for metabolism and to improve the nutrition process. Direct mechanisms include nitrogen fixation (N); synthesis of phytohormones, vitamins, and enzymes, the solubilization of inorganic phosphorus (P) and the mineralization of organic phosphate, the oxidation of sulfides, the increase in root permeability, nitrite production, nitrate accumulation, reducing heavy metal toxicity and enzyme activity ACC deaminase, secretion of siderophores, reduced levels of ethylene in soils, and increased root permeability. Whereas, the indirect mechanisms are characterized by the fact that the PGPR causes the reduction or elimination of phytopathogenic microorganisms [43].

Through the production of antimicrobial substances or antibiotics, lytic enzymes or by nutrient competition or of space in the ecological niche, as well as by stimulation of the natural defenses from the plant through biocontrol mechanisms; induced systemic resistance (ISR) to a broad spectrum of pathogens and the production of siderophores, as a mechanism to sequester the Fe available in the soils and with this limit the development and the presence of phytopathogens; production of antibiotics and hydrogen cyanides that impact on the phytopathogens; hydrolysis of molecules such as fusaric acid generated to release 1-3-glucanase, with which the development of the fungal wall is inhibition of fungi such as *Pythium ultimum* and *Rhizoctonia solani*. One of the limitations of PGPRs is that the beneficial effect they pose on a certain plant species is not the same for other plants [44].

Functions of PGPR

The direct and indirect mechanisms of action used by PGPRs are further explained according to their function as biofertilizers, phyto stimulators, and biocontrol.

Biofertilization: Improving soil fertility has been one of the different strategies to increase agricultural production. However, over time, it has become evident the importance of the use of synthetic fertilizers. It has not turned out to be the expected panacea, since of the total of fertilizers applied only 10 to 40% is assimilated by plants and, because the loss of soil fertility, in the system, has forced producers to increase the use of these fertilizers to maintain their production, at the cost of increasing production costs and environmental impacts. As a result of the rising cost of synthetic fertilizers, there are few natural reserves of some minerals and high energy consumption.

For its production, the use of biological alternatives has been promoted, such as a necessity in agricultural production today and in the future, without affecting the environment, in addition to economic feasibility. Biofertilizers are all those products that contain microorganisms alive, with the capacity to colonize the rhizosphere or the interior of the plants, applied to the ground or in the plant via foliar spraying, through inoculation, can live associated or in symbiosis with plant species and help them in their nutrition and protection. They are intended to replace the application of synthetic fertilizers and reduce their polluting effect partially or totally. Biofertilizers do not directly supply any nutritive element to the crops and sources are bioproducts, made mainly from bacteria [45].

Atmospheric Nitrogen Fixation: Biological nitrogen fixation is limited to prokaryotes that possess, unlike the plant, a nitrogenase enzyme complex, which consists of two proteins dinitrogenase and dinitrogenase reductase: both contain Fe in its structure, dinitrogenase, in addition, contains Mo that catalyzes the reduction of atmospheric N in ammonia. Microbiological activation of atmospheric nitrogen generates ammonia, which ionizes the ammonium cation (NH_4^+), via hydrolysis of ATP and reducing power transfer coupled to an electron transport chain. Bacteria that fix atmospheric N in ammonium are biologically usable, called diazotrophic. Diazotrophic organisms include a wide range of Archaea and bacteria that colonize various plant species, in a wide variety of ecosystems [46].

Among symbiotic rhizospheric prokaryotic bacteria that fix N, in association with legumes, there is the rhizobia group, for example, *Rhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Sinorhizobium*, *Azorhizobium*, *Mesorhizobium*, and *Allorhizobium*, and the *Frankia strains*, belonging to the genus Streptomycetaceae, filamentous sporulation bacteria associated with actinorhizal plants, especially genera *Alnus* and *Casuarina*. For more than a century, the symbiosis between bacteria of the genus *Rhizobium* and legumes has been considered the most efficient way to fix atmospheric N, making it available to plants. Due to the importance of the biological nitrogen fixation process, regardless of whether it is due to symbiosis or symbiotic form, the incorporation of this element promotes the stimulation of microbial processes during the decomposition of organic matter and the recycling of essential nutritive elements within productive agricultural systems, as well as those treated as sustainable agriculture [47].

Solubilization of phosphates: Phosphorous is one of the main essential macronutrients, and its deficiency limits crucially the growth of plants. Like for N, today it can be asserted that some PGPR, specifically the phosphate solubilizing bacteria, solubilize the insoluble phosphates of soils and make them available to plants and well, in turn, provides them with carbon compounds that are metabolized for microbial growth as well as root exudates and plant detritus supply the energy substrate that favors its activity as a solubilizer [48].

These bacteria constitute 1 to 50% of the total microbial population of soils. It is also necessary to highlight that some microorganisms that solubilize phosphates from the soil, can also present other activities of promoting plant growth substances such as indoleacetic acid production (IAA), gibberellic acid, hydrogen cyanide (HCN), cytokinins, and ethylene. The main bacterial genera solubilizers of phosphates are *Achromobacter*, *Acinetobacter*, *Agrobacterium*, *Bacillus*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Enterobacter*, *Erwinia*, *Klebsiella*, *Mesorhizobium*, *Micrococci*, *Mycobacterium*, *Pseudomonas*, *Sinorhizobium*, and *Streptomyces*. This group includes the bacterial genera that solubilize phosphates due to their ability to produce organic acids, among which are the acids: acetic, adipic, citric, formic, fumaric, glycolic, gluconic, indoleacetic, lactic, malic, malonic, oxalic, propionic, succinic and 2-ketogluconic. The best frequently reported phosphate solubilizers are gluconic and 2-ketogluconic. Most of the organic acids produced by these are aliphatic (non-aromatic acids). These acids modify the pH causing the dissolution of insoluble phosphates in soils. In addition to having a direct action on the acidification, chelation, precipitation, and oxide-reduction reactions of the rhizosphere, acids form complexes with metals, solubilize metals and participate in their uptake [49].

The solubilization of these minerals may be because acids lower the pH and, even more, the formation of stable complexes with cations such as Ca^{+2} , Mg^{+2} , Fe^{+3} , and Al^{+3} . The effect of organic acids also affects the phosphates incorporated into the soil, through synthetic fertilizers, reducing the precipitation of these phosphates by Fe and Al. In soils, the solubilization of phosphate by organic acids is dependent on the pH and its mineralogy, and this process is carried out by two mechanisms:

1. In an acid exchange, for example, the H^+ ions from citrate are exchanged from the bound phosphorus to the surface of the $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ crystals, reducing them and releasing the P.
2. The other mechanism is dependent on the concentration of organic acids produced by phosphate solubilizing bacteria; the amount and type of organic acids released depend on the type of microorganisms, the chelating effect of these acids in solubilization consists that through their hydroxyl and carboxyl groups sequester the cations attached to the phosphate converting it to soluble forms.

Inoculation with the microorganisms increases the availability of phosphorus in the rhizosphere and its absorption by the plant. A reduction of 50% in the appli-

cation of P fertilizers could be achieved by using a combination of P and PGPR solubilizing microorganisms without affecting crop performance. On the other hand, the introduction of genes overexpressed in bacteria from the rhizosphere to solubilize phosphates, and the improvement of the capacity of microorganisms as inoculants, has caught the attention of researchers [50].

Production of Siderophores: Siderophores are small molecules produced by microorganisms under Fe-limiting conditions that increase their entry into the microbial cell. Commonly, bacteria acquire Fe through the secretion of low molecular weight Fe chelates called siderophores, which are in constant association with Fe complexes. In addition to their low molecular weight, these compounds are soluble in aqueous solutions at neutral pH and can be fluorescent. Various organisms synthesize small molecules, non-ribosomal peptides, of high affinity for Fe^{+3} that act specifically as chelating agents to sequester Fe in the presence of other metals and cause its reduction to Fe^{+2} which is a much more soluble and usable form for the nutrition of these organisms [51].

The kidnapping of the Fe by microorganisms, under conditions of scarcity, develops as follows: once the Fe is sequestered from the surrounding environment, the siderophore-Fe complex is recognized by specific receptors of the microbial membrane, and once inside the cells, it is deposited at a specific site by a process that involves an exchange of ligands that can be preceded or not by the reduction of Fe or by the hydrolysis of the siderophore. The presence of the siderophores would represent a great advantage for the microorganisms since they could acquire Fe from the environment that surrounds them more easily than the rest of their competitors [52].

Production of exopolysaccharides: The ability to produce, secrete or exude polysaccharides is another of the multiple benefits that PGPRs possess. These exudates include polysaccharides: structural, intracellular, and extracellular or exopolysaccharides (EPS), which are composed mainly of carbohydrates, forming homo or heteropolymers, and can contain organic and inorganic substituents. These products offer advantages such as the great versatility of microorganisms to synthesize neutral or negatively charged polysaccharides, from renewable sources, under controlled conditions and the possibility of genetic manipulation, with which it can be possible to obtain products with better functional properties and even higher quality. PGPRs in the rhizosphere of a plant participate in the enhancement of the stabilization via the exopolysaccharide layer which is a hydrated gel around the cell and provide insulation to microbe from the external environment [53].

The production of high levels of EPS, by certain bacteria, allows the plants to better withstand adverse environments. Exopolysaccharide is related to the water transfer from the soil into the roots and so does the pore size. Therefore, PGPR control this activity and so does the water transfer, retaining the water film intact which is important for photosynthetic activity, aeration, and protection from environmental pollutants, stress, and pathogens. Under water scarcity, exopolysaccharide-producing bacteria can limit the loss of water i.e.,

under saline conditions. Moreover, PGPR also acts as signal molecules to produce plant growth-promoting substances of phytohormones like auxin, cytokinin, ethylene, and gibberellins [54].

These substances are indicator molecules that act as chemical messengers that influence the ability of plants to respond to their environment. Regulate expression of genes involved in plant growth and development, which are synthesized in different plant structures and their action varies depending on environmental changes that modify the organism's gene expression and are generally effective in small concentrations. It has been established that they are also involved in the avenues of catabolic repression and regulation of biofilm formation [55].

Even these molecules exhibit specific effects on plant physiology, such as increasing the root volume, increasing the respiration rate of the plant root host, and proton flux in the root membrane; consequently, favor the absorption of soluble mineral elements. However, although phytohormones are known to regulate plant development and their physiology, as well as immunity, their production by microorganisms has not been considered a biological control mechanism.

Certain PGPR not only offers tolerance under stress conditions in plants but also can promote growth in them even under adverse conditions. Heavy metal contamination is a worldwide problem and threatens human life by polluting agricultural land with metals like cadmium, copper, mercury, lead, etc. These metals leach down to water reserves as well entering the ecosystem with their poisonous effects on biotic as well as abiotic elements of the environment. Phytoremediation is the technology that employs the uptake of these metals from soil into plants via a mechanism to immobilize or transform these metals into less toxic states. These mechanisms, also called phytoremediation, is a relatively new technology offering clear advantages over traditional methods for cleaning contaminated sites [56]. The above-explained mechanisms can be illustrated in figure 1.

Heavy metal stress and its effects

Heavy metals have various chemical, physical, and biological properties for different environments. In total, sixty-five different heavy metals occur in nature performing essential functions as well as growth, reproduction, etc. However, the increase in particular concentration can lead to toxic effects [26]. The Agency of United States Environmental Protection (EPA) has defined Hg (a trace heavy metal) as dangerous, a slight exposure to this metal may cause damage to human health. Another nine metals have been defined as possible hazard elements: Ba, Cd, Cu, Pb, Mn, Ni, Zn, Vn, and Sn, which are dangerous in potential and must be

maintained under control. All of these except the manganese are trace metals, and all except barium, are heavy metals. In soils, the most abundant metals are Mn, Zn, Ni, and Pb ($1-1,500 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$); Mn can reach $10,000 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$. Heavy metals can be found in high centers on soils due to natural causes. Ultrabasic igneous rocks (such as the peridotites and the streamers) present the highest content of heavy metals, followed by the basic igneous rocks (such as gabbros and basalts). Heavy metals incorporated into soil can pass into surface waters or underground, into the atmosphere by volatilization, to the trophic chains when being absorbed by plants or being retained, so that pose a biological threat to all organisms [57]. The processes of bioaccumulation are basically due to the impossibility of the affected organism maintaining the necessary levels of excretion of the pollutant, so it suffers tension inside the same [5].

Remediation techniques: Phytoremediation

Technological advances to sanitize environments contaminated by toxic metals have led to the development of alternatives based on the employment of organizations to prevent or restore damage caused by anthropogenic actions that alter the stability of different ecosystems. In this sense, bioremediation is a natural procedure that consists of the use of biological systems capable of removing organic pollutants unique and inorganic of a given medium, given its ability to use compositions present in their environment and make them precursors of their constituents' cells. Phytoremediation is one of the versions of bioremediation that can be considered an alternative and sustainable technology [58]. In this process, the plants (arboreal, shrubby, herbaceous flora) and algae used have the capacity of storing and disposing of toxic substances through their metabolic processes, principally heavy metals, so they are called hyperaccumulating plants [56]. There are several phytoremediation techniques applicable to soils contaminated with heavy metals: phytoextraction, Phytostabilization, phytodegradation, phytovolatilization, and phyto-restoration [59]. In this sense, phytoremediation includes:

- Phytovolatilization is the transference of the air pollutant through plant perspiration [60].
- Phytoextraction, also known as phytoaccumulation, consists of the absorption and translocation of metals from the roots to the aerial parts of the plants [61]. The Phytostabilization is based on the use of tolerant plants to immobilize metals through their absorption and accumulation in the roots or precipitation in the rhizosphere, and distribution reducing their mobility and bioavailability for other plants or microorganisms in soils where a large amount of pollutants makes phytoextraction impossible [62].

Figure 1 Plant Growth Promoting Rhizomicrobes play an important role in eradicating contaminants especially heavy metals from soil

- Phyto-degradation and phytodegradation refer to the degradation of organic pollutants unique through plant enzymes, their products, or by the action of rhizospheres' microorganisms. Phyto-restoration is referred to the reforestation of polluted areas with resistant species of fast growth, which prevent the migration of pollutant particles and the erosion of soils. Degradation of the rhizosphere is the decomposition of organic pollutants within the rhizosphere rich in microbes (soil surrounding the root) [63].

- Hydraulic control:** the use of trees to intercept and perspire large quantities of ground or surface water to contain or control the migration of pollutants [64].

Plants capture toxic substances through various mechanisms. This occurs through highly specific procedures with a great capacity to absorb different pollutants. The employment potential of plant hyperaccumulators of heavy metals in the remediation of contaminated soils is limited by certain factors. In general, the metals with the highest bioavailability for absorption by aquatic plant stimulators are Cd, Ni, Zn, As Se, and Cu. With moderate behavior are the Co, Mn, and Fe, while Pb and Cr are practically not bioavailable [65].

Hyperaccumulator plants

Plants that can grow and develop in soils with high concentrations of heavy metals belong to a specialized flora, which colonizes native soil i.e., Ni and calamine (minerals that contain high concentrations of Zn and Cd), natural or are contaminated by anthropogenic activity like mining activity. Those plants are naturally selected for their high tolerance to a certain metal (hyper tolerance) [66]. About 415 have been identified as hyperaccumulator plant species being distributed in 45 botanical families with the capacity to selectively accu-

mulate some substances. Hyperaccumulators are species capable of accumulating metals to levels 100 times more than those typically measured in plant suckers not accumulated [67].

Three types of mechanisms have been distinguished in hyperaccumulating plants: accumulation, indicator, and exclusion. These mechanisms allow them to tolerate high values of metallic elements that are toxic to other plant species. The type and composition of the soil, characteristics of organic substances and inorganic substances and their chelating power, the value and pH range, the redox state, as well as the rhizosphere soil-plant interactions occupy a central place in the relationships of availability, toxicity, and the response of plants to heavy metals [68]. Not all organs of the plant have the same significance in the accumulation of heavy metals. Normally, the root is the priority body for entry and accumulation. In many species, there is fine subcellular compartmentalization, especially in the vacuole and cell wall [69].

Soil microorganisms and phytoextraction of metals

Phytoremediation demands the study of the microbial communities of the soil hyper-accumulated with heavy metal and their interactions. Soil microorganisms are very important because they intervene in the trace element cycles, or they are responsible for the mobilization of metals and their accumulation [70]. The microorganisms are sensitive both to deficiencies such as excessive concentrations of metallic elements, reducing their growth and enzymatic activity, but at the same time, they can adapt to them. The rhizosphere is defined as the narrow soil zone surrounding the root (approximately 1-2 mm distance) [25]. The rhizosphere

microorganisms perform important functions in biogeochemical cycles of elements such as nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, iron, and other metals, as well as the fertility of plants, protection against pathogens, degradative function of compounds, and production of phytohormones. The degradative capacity of the rhizospheres' micro biota can be used in soil bioremediation as an attractive technology for its low cost. Bioremediation techniques that use microorganisms can be combined with the use of plants (phytoremediation). This resulting combination is of great interest to increase the efficiency in the extraction of pollutants. These techniques are called rhizoremediation [71].

In general, the group of bacteria that favor the growth of plants is known as Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR). This term has been accepted to describe bacteria that can colonize roots intensively and can exert a positive effect on crops. The microbial mechanisms that benefit plant growth include direct or indirect motion. The direct manifest itself through an increase in nutrient availability and uptake of mineral substances or provision of drivers of growth. However, indirect occurs through the deletion of harmful microorganisms in the rhizosphere [72]. PGPRs can increase the growth of plants in different ways:

- By associative nitrogen fixation
- Phosphate solubilization
- Stimulation of the functions of mycorrhizae
- Regulation of ethylene production in the roots
- Release of phytohormones
- Reducing the toxicity of heavy metals.

A special niche for the microorganism-plant association is constituted by heavy metal accumulating in plants. In this sense, the association of rhizospheres and endophytic bacteria requires specific adaptations such as high heavy metal levels [66].

Among the functions of microorganisms, they are symbiotic with plant roots, metal accumulators, promote mobility and availability of metals to plants by producing siderophores, reduce the pH of the soil by the action of organic acids, solubilize phosphates, produce plant growth-promoting properties (phytohormones), and be resistant to heavy metals, drugs, and antibiotics. Several pieces of evidence suggested that soil microorganisms possess mechanisms that alter the mobility of metal pollutants in the environment, with subsequent effects on the potential for root uptake. Microorganisms can detoxify metals by transformation in their oxidation number, extracellular and chemical precipitation, or volatilization [73].

Penicillium possesses the ability to precipitate a variety of heavy metals such as Cu, Ni, Pb, and Cd [74]. These properties have prompted some researchers to propose the use of microorganisms to remove metal poisons from contaminated soils. Many data indicate that soil microorganisms have the potential to alter the metal uptake range and accumulation in plants. Microorganisms that catalyze transformations that lead to changes in the bioavailability of metals in the soil and the potential for phytoextraction have been reported. Studies carried out in the communities of bacteria isolated from soil areas of the rhizosphere of *Alyssum bertolonii*, indicated the presence of bacteria representatives of the group of α proteo-bacteria that possess great genetic diversity and heterogeneity in populations of bacteria that live under these unfavorable conditions. The highest values of genetic diversity were found at 5 and 10cm away from the plant. Their role in the mobilization of heavy metals and their availability to accumulate in plants of these soils.

The isolates that were more resistant to Ni^{2+} belonged to the genera *Pseudomonas*, *Azotobacter*, and *Herbaspirillum*. Other studies reported on the bacterial resistance to Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} of bacteria isolated from the contaminated soils from where isolated 24 heterotrophic bacteria with high resistance to these metals, and was found a predominance of bacteria populations (73%), followed in decreasing order by filamentous fungal populations (18%) and yeast (9%). The most represented bacteria were *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* and among filamentous fungi in the genus *Aspergillus* [75].

Metal-microbiota interactions are deeply studied in the context of environmental biotechnology, to implement removal methods and reduction or detoxification of heavy metals and radionuclides. Inside of wide microbial diversity, there are resistant microorganisms and microorganisms are tolerant to metals. The resistant ones are characterized by mechanisms of genetically encoded detoxification, induced by the presence of metal. On the other hand, tolerant microorganisms are indifferent to the presence of metal. Both microorganisms are resistant as the tolerant are of particular interest particularly in contaminated sites because both can extract the contaminants. Phytoremediation is a highly promising technique for the sanitation and restoration of soils with a high concentration of heavy metals [76]. These techniques are mentioned in figure 2 as a summary.

Figure 2 Phytoremediation techniques are used in the remediation of soil to remove heavy metal contamination

Effective microorganisms (EM)

Effective microorganisms consist of liquid-formulated products that contain more than 80 species of microorganisms, some species are aerobic, anaerobic, and even photosynthetic species whose main achievement is that they can coexist as microbial communities [77].

Effective microorganisms play role in bioremediation processes of waste treatment, removal of odors, and agricultural waste management of different industries [78].

In his trials and experiments, he gathered about 2000 species of microorganisms, of which 80 showed effective effects. By accident, the doctor placed a mixture of the EMs in small bushes and after time he observed an important stimulus in the growth of the same. In 1982, the professor presented a commercial formulation known as EM for the biological conditioning of soils. As a technology, EMs consists of the mixed microbial culture of selected species of microorganisms that coexist at an approximate pH of 3.5 [79].

Alleviation of phytopathogens' effects

The use of microbial consortia has proven to be efficient in the control of soil phyto nematodes. Microorganisms associated with the rhizosphere of plants facilitate the growth, development, and functioning of vital processes such as promoting plant growth and protecting plants from Phyto parasitic agents. In the rhizosphere, EM compete for the available resources and reside at different root zones preventing phytopathogens to attack or occupy the root area. Their efficiency can also be controlled by various suppressive mechanisms like production of antimicrobial compounds, siderophores, and metabolites [80].

Currently, for the formulation of phosphate solubilizing bioinoculants, it is a matter of having other functional activities such as the promotion of plant

growth [81]. The terrestrial environment is constantly changing, and this contributes to the natural forces of selection producing modifications in organisms. In the case of plants, these modifications allow them to adapt to new environmental conditions through genetic changes in populations during a period governed by natural selection. The evolutionary process can be analyzed on two levels: microevolution and macroevolution. Microevolution consists of evolutionary changes produced in species in relatively short periods due to the force of natural selection, while macroevolution involves evolutionary changes between species and generally occurs after long periods. An example of microevolution in plant organisms is the development of tolerance to metals. In this process, anthropogenic activities act as the selection force that generates evolutionary changes in organisms, in relatively short periods (hundreds or decades of years) [82].

Tolerance to potentially toxic elements (essential and non-essential metals) in plant organisms can be defined as the result of an evolutionary process that gives different plant species the ability to grow and develop in environments with high concentrations of potentially toxic elements. The evolutionary changes that have given rise to tolerance are due to the development of a series of efficient and specific mechanisms (adaptive processes) that allow maintaining the intake of essential elements within permissible physiological intervals, in addition to providing the ability to metabolically inactivate the elements. essential and nonessential when they pose a risk to cell integrity [83].

Tolerance of plants to environmental pollutants

Tolerance is classified into two types according to the set of molecular or biochemical mechanisms that make it up:

1. Co-tolerance may be the result of a specific mechanism that confers tolerance to various metals [84].

2. Multiple tolerance, in which tolerance is generated by a series of independent mechanisms for each metal or metal that interact together to prevent damage to the plant [85].

Of these two ideas, the evidence suggests that multiple tolerance is the type that occurs in most plants [86]. The presence of multiple tolerance has allowed plants to develop three basic strategies to establish themselves in soils with toxic levels of metals [26]:

1. Exclusion: this strategy consists of a limited accumulation of metals in the aerial parts of the plants and involves a preferential accumulation in the root system.

2. Indicators: this strategy is characterized by the fact that plants accumulate metals in their tissues that generally reflect the levels of metals present in the soil.

3. Hyperaccumulation: this strategy is characterized by the plant's ability to bioaccumulate high concentrations of metals in its tissues, mainly in the aerial parts.

Considering the criterion of the presence of multiple tolerance in plants [87], the possible mechanisms of tolerance are divided into the following ways:

- External mechanisms of tolerance
- Internal mechanisms of tolerance

External mechanisms of tolerance via Mycorrhizal fungi (MF)

The external mechanism of tolerance takes place through mycorrhizal fungi. In plants, the metal adsorption process can be influenced by microorganisms that are closely associated with the root (rhizospheres' community). Among these microorganisms, mycorrhizal fungi (MF) constitute one of the most important components of the rhizosphere since they form mutualistic associations (mycorrhizae) with various plant species. MF can be classified into two groups according to the type of colonization of the host plant: arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), which are characterized by intracellularly colonizing the root system of 80% of plant species, and ectomycorrhizal fungi (EMF), which are characterized by extracellular root colonization of 3% of plant species [88]. In the case of EMF, the mechanisms that can be present are (1) mobility of the metal in the apoplast, preventing entry to the root; (2) reduction of metal mobility in the apoplast as a result of the hydrophobicity of the fungus; (3) secretion of chelating substances such as organic acids and other substances produced by EMF; and (4) retention of metals in the outer mycelium of the fungus [89].

In the case of EMF, the mechanisms are (1) extracellular immobilization of metals by organic acids (OA); (2) reduction of ion transfer from the radical system to the stem, by intracellular precipitation of the metal by PO_4^{3-} ; and (3) adsorption of metal ions on the cell wall of different structures of the fungus (hypha, spores, extra radical mycelium) and retention of the metal in the mycorrhizosphere by the production of specific proteins (e.g. glomalin) [90]. However, some factors can affect tolerance to metals during the MF-plant association. Among these factors the species of plant

and fungus used, the type of metal and its availability, the cultivation conditions of the plant, and the density of the root system can be explored. This has been observed in mycorrhizal plants of *Pinus sylvestris*, in which a reduction of zinc (Zn) is generated in their root system when inoculated with *Paxillus involutus*; however, when using *Thelephora terrestris* (another species of EMF) the opposite effect is generated. Furthermore, in other EMF species, *Suillus bovinus*, and *T. terrestris*, both organisms have been observed to protect their host from Cu, but vary in their metal retention capacity [91].

Internal mechanisms of tolerance

The internal mechanism of tolerance takes place through the following:

- a) Binding to the cell wall and radical exudates,
- b) Chelation of metals by cytosolic ligands,
- c) Presence of thermal stress proteins,
- d) Accumulation in the vacuole.

Radical exudates and cell wall binding: Various studies have shown that radical exudates are formed mainly by low molecular weight organic acids (OA), generated mainly from the tricarboxylic acid cycle. The importance of OA in tolerance to metals in the radical system is that they can influence the solubility of essential and non-essential elements directly through acidification, chelation, precipitation, and oxidation-reduction processes in the rhizosphere, and indirectly through effects on microbial activity, on the physical properties of the rhizosphere and root growth dynamics. The participation of OAs in metal tolerance is observed mainly in plants exposed to aluminum. This was illustrated in one of the studies that when exposing *Fagopyrum esculentum* plants to aluminum (Al) [92], higher production of oxalic acid was associated with tolerance to Al, by preventing its entry into the cell. Similar results were indicated in 2005 that an increase in the flow of oxalic acid to the root system of *Spinacia oleracea* cv. plants treated with Al, but not when they were exposed to a deficiency of phosphorus and an excess of Al [25].

Regarding the participation of organic acids (OA) in tolerance to other metals, an accumulation of citrate in the radical exudates of non-hyper-accumulating plants was observed, which contributes to lower absorption of Ni during prolonged exposure to this metal through the formation and precipitation of OA-Ni complexes in the rhizosphere. However, in hyperaccumulating plants of Cd (*Thlaspi caerulescens*) and Ni (*Alysum bertolonii*) it has been observed that there is a contrary result. Due to the high presence of citric, malic, and oxalic acids in the lateral roots, the formation of OA-metal complexes in the rhizosphere is stimulated, facilitating the absorption and intracellular retention of metals in the radical system, as well as the transport to tissue vacuoles using tonoplast membrane proteins [93].

The production of OA in plants is possibly generated when the metal encounters the root apex, activating the flow of OA, which allows its entry into the cell by different routes. Regardless of the steps followed by the metal, there is an induction of OA metabolism, and the protonation of organic compounds takes place, which is sent to the cytosol where they form complexes

with non-essential cations. Furthermore, cytosolic pH is kept stable through the coordinated function of OA transporters and K channels [94].

The idea that cell wall components such as cellulose and lignin can contribute to metal tolerance in plants was proposed around 1970. Since then, various studies have been carried out in which it is proposed that the structural arrangement of cellulose and lignin allows them to form covalent bonds through their oxygen atoms with metals, sequestering them in the apoplast. It was observed that the sequestration of metals such as Zn, Cu, and Cd in the cell wall of the root of *Phragmites australis* and *Zea mays* is related to a greater lignification of the radical cells [50]. The authors attribute this effect to the increased activity of peroxidase that stimulates lignin biosynthesis in response to stress caused by these metals.

Despite these results, the participation of the cell wall as a mechanism of tolerance to heavy metals in plants is controversial. When the cell wall is directly in contact with the metals present in the soil, the absorption of the metal by it can be limited. However, this does not seem to apply to algae, since for these organisms' various authors believe that the retention of metals by the cell wall seems to be one of the main mechanisms of tolerance. This difference is since the cell wall of the algae is made up of numerous microfibrillar layers of cellulose and alginates (a polymer-rich in sulfate groups that constitutes between 20 and 40% of the biomass) in the form of gels, which gives it a high metal bio-adsorption capacity [95].

Chelation of metals in the cytosol by various ligands: Chelation can be defined as the ability of a molecule to complex with metal and thus form a new compound with different chemical properties from the original. Chelation is a homeostatic process in which two types of molecules participate: (1) transporter molecules, responsible for transferring specific metal ions to particular organelles such as vacuoles, chloroplasts, and mitochondria that require them; and (2) high-affinity ligands such as phytochelatins, metallothionein, organic acids, heat stress proteins, and amino acids, which contribute to detoxification while keeping the concentration of metal ions in the cytosol stable [96].

a) **Phytochelatins (PCs):** The best-characterized high-affinity ligands in plant cells are phytochelatins (PCs) and metallothionein (MT). PCs have been identified in a wide variety of plants, certain microorganisms, and fungi. In plants, phytochelatins are peptides with the general formula $(\gamma - \text{Glu} - \text{Cys})_n - \text{Gly}$ ($n = 2-11$), where the structures $(\gamma - \text{Glu} - \text{Cys})_2 - \text{Gly}$ (FQ 2) and $(\gamma - \text{Glu} - \text{Cys})_3 - \text{Gly}$ (FQ 3) are the most common. The PCs were first detected in 1981, and the formation of complexes of peptides with cadmium ions in the yeast *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* was observed, which they called 'cadistins'. On the other hand, the presence of peptides with a high degree of polymerization in various plant cell cultures exposed to cadmium ions was also observed which were called 'phytochelatinins' [97].

The synthesis of PCs in plants is carried out enzymatically from γ -glutamyl cysteine dipeptidyl transpeptidase, commonly called phytochelatin synthase,

which is constitutively expressed but can also be regulated at the transcriptional and post-transcriptional level. The substrate of PCs is glutathione (GSH), whose synthesis can be affected by oxidative stress and is produced by two reactions catalyzed by γ -glutamyl cysteine synthetase and GSH synthetase from glutamine (Glu), cysteine (Cys) and glycine (Gly) [98].

The mechanism of action of PCs in plants consists of the formation of non-toxic complexes with metal ions through interaction with thiol groups of cysteine (Cys), forming a low molecular weight metal-PC complex, which later binds to sulfide ions (S_2^-) in the cytosol, stabilizing the complex, and further forms complex high molecular weight molecules [99]. These molecules subsequently cross the tonoplast, possibly using ABC transporters; once inside the vacuole, the organic acids present (malate, citrate, oxalate) retain the metal ions and dissociate the PC-metal complex. It is not yet clear what happens to the PCs once separated from the metal; however, it was suggested that possibly PCs can be degraded in the vacuole or returned to the cytoplasm to form new complexes with metal ions [96,100].

In aquatic and terrestrial plant organisms, there is evidence that shows that PCs play an important role in the detoxification of different metals because high concentrations of different ions can stimulate their synthesis; PCs sequester metals (essential and non-essential) and distribute them preferentially to the vacuole of the different tissues. However, its role in tolerance is not clear and can vary between species of plant organisms and the type of metal, as it was found that when inhibiting the activity of the enzyme PC synthase (key to the synthesis of PC) in plants tolerant to Co, Ni, Cu and Zn, no variations were observed in their tolerance capacity, which suggests the participation of other mechanisms in the process of homeostatic regulation [101]. On the other hand, it was suggested that PCs not only play an important role in the detoxification of metals but also participate in the mitigation of oxidative stress [102].

b) **Metallothionein:** Metallothionein (MTS) are proteins of low molecular weight (4–8 kDa), generated transcriptionally and with the ability to bind metal ions (due to their high content of cysteine residues, 30% of the total protein) to avoid this metal poisoning. Their discovery is around 40 years old, and they were firstly described as a type of Cd chelating protein in horse liver. The genes that code for MTS have been detected in animals (vertebrates and invertebrates), plants, and some prokaryotes. MTS are classified into two classes, considering the amino acid sequences that make them up. The MT1 class includes only mammalian MTs, while the MT2 class includes the MTs of fungi, invertebrates, and plants. To understand the regulation of MTs, the expression of their genes has been studied in some plants using molecular biology techniques [103].

Class II MTs present in plants are grouped into four types (Mt1, Mt2, Mt3, Mt4) according to the ordering of cysteine residues in the protein and were identified for the first time in mature wheat embryos as a Zn 'chelating' protein. Since the discovery of MTS in plants, his study has been focused on evaluating the expression of genes in different stages of the development of terrestrial plants, mainly in angiosperms, a group in

which it has been found that the expression of MTs may be restricted in different plant tissues. For example, the presence of Mt4 was identified in corn seeds as a possible mechanism to provide the required micronutrients during germination [100].

In the case of Mt1, a greater induction of messenger RNA (mRNA) was observed in the roots of *Arabidopsis thaliana*, while the expression of the Mt2 gene in the same plant presented a greater induction of mRNA in the stem and leaves than in the roots [104]. In the case of the Mt3 gene, it was observed that there was overexpression in the leaves of plants such as *Arabidopsis thaliana* and plants such as banana, kiwi, and apple [100].

The mechanism of action of MTs in homeostatic regulation and tolerance to metals in plants is not fully established. However, its participation in metal tolerance has been recognized in different plant species, such as *Oryza sativa* and *Arabidopsis thaliana* when treated with Cu, Cd, and Zn, species in which a higher expression was observed [105].

Presence of thermal stress proteins: In plants, heat shock proteins (HSPs) are in different cell compartments and are classified into six different classes according to their location: in the cytosol and nucleus (class 1, 2, and 3), in chloroplasts, in the mitochondria or associated with the endoplasmic reticulum. The role of HSPs *in vivo* has not been fully understood, but it is believed that cytosol HSPs may act to protect cells from the toxic or lethal effect of heat, preventing protein denaturation during stress and facilitating their subsequent reactivation. However, their function as chaperones has also been demonstrated *in vivo* and *in vitro* experiments [106].

Regarding the participation of these proteins in metal tolerance, it was observed that the effect of Pb and Ni in isolated chloroplasts of two varieties of *Agrostis stolonifera* produced a higher content of HSP in chloroplasts of the tolerant variety [107], generating greater protection of the photosynthetic system [108]. These results show a specific protective function by HSPs to stress caused by metals in this plant. On the

other hand, in one study, it was found that when exposing *Hordeum vulgare* and *Zea mays* plants to Cd, a greater induction of the HSP17 gene was generated, located in the cytoplasm [109], which was related to the protection and repair of proteins during metal exposure [5,110].

Regarding the synthesis of HSPs in plants exposed to metals, it has been proposed that it may be caused by oxidative stress generated by metals since there is a relationship between heat and the presence of reactive species. This has been observed that reactive oxygen species induce thermo-tolerance in plants, later on, it was confirmed that the generation of reactive oxygen species in the body produces heat pulses that stimulate the production of HSPs proteins in cells [106,111].

Storage of metals in the vacuole: The vacuole has been described as a cellular component that occupies about 80% of the volume of the cell, although there may also be smaller vacuoles, which can be distinguished by the content of soluble proteins and by their membrane protein (aquaporins). Vacuoles serve as a reservoir for metabolites and nutrients and participate in the process of homeostatic regulation of the cytosol [112]. The importance of the vacuole in metal tolerance has been demonstrated in various works. For example, in 1991 it was observed that there was a correlation between tolerance and greater vacuolization of root meristem cells in *Festuca rubra* plants when exposed to Zn [113]. Later, in metal absorption studies using Zn in the leaf tissue of *Hordeum vulgare* plants, rapid storage of Zn in the vacuole was suggested to be an important mechanism to avoid tissue damage from high concentrations of the metal [114].

Tonoplast has also been shown to be a key factor in metal tolerance, as confirmed when exposed to Zn, the isolated tonoplasts of tolerant and non-tolerant plants to the metal noted that the transport through the tonoplast by membrane proteins to the vacuole was 2.5 times higher in tolerant plants, confirming the importance of the vacuole in tolerance to metals in plants [115]. All these techniques are summarized in figure 3.

Figure 3 The tolerance of plants is explained in the following figure via internal and external mechanisms of tolerance

Conclusion

To summarize this article, heavy metals can be compartmentalized via different plant-microbe interaction techniques. The increase in residues with potentially toxic elements in the environment is an important factor that has caused plants to develop a wide range of mechanisms to be able to grow in environments with high concentrations of essential and non-essential elements. The prevalence of one mechanism or another in the plant is not yet fully understood. Therefore, it is necessary for the future to carry out studies that involve the application of molecular and biochemical tools, as well as model plants such as *Arabidopsis* or *Thlaspi caeroleus*, to understand more clearly the mode of action of the heavy metals tolerance mechanisms in the homeostatic maintenance of the plant cell. This review shows the importance of knowing the biochemical and molecular bases of the different tolerance mechanisms that plants have developed to survive in environments with high concentrations of potentially toxic elements. This type of knowledge will allow feasible solutions to the problems of pollution and the possibility of recovery of the different ecosystems impacted by metals. Efficient microorganisms comprise a great microbial diversity represented by lactic acid bacteria, photosynthetic bacteria, yeasts, actinomycetes, and filamentous fungi with fermentative activity. Efficient microorganisms have numerous agricultural applications because they functionally favor seed germination, increase flowering, increase growth and development of fruits, increase biomass, guarantee successful reproduction in plants, improve the physical structure of soils, increase their chemical fertility, and suppress various disease-causing phytopathogens. Efficient microorganisms in-

crease photosynthetic activity and the absorption of water and nutrients in plants, they also reduce the maturation times of organic fertilizers, particularly composting, which offers important agricultural applications. Therefore, these remediation techniques should be incorporated on the field level to test their effectiveness and reduce environmental pollution and soil infertility by heavy metals.

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